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PEDIATRIC BURNS IN WAR

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the clinical characteristics of pediatric cases brought to our country due to burns caused by the Syrian civil war and to contribute to the literature with the obtained findings. This study was conducted as a single-center, retrospective analysis covering burn cases under the age of 18 who were hospitalized in the Hatay Education and Research Hospital Burn Unit between 01.01. 2011-31.12.2024. Age, gender, cause of burn, degree and percentage of burns, burn areas, presence of additional interventions, length of stay, and mortality status of the patients were evaluated. The median age of 984 pediatric burn patients in our study was 7 years, and 79.2% were male. The most common cause of burns was flame (72.4%), followed by scalding (25.4%) and electrical/contact (2.2%) burns. The median total burn surface area was 23%, the most frequently affected areas were the anterior trunk, head and neck, and upper extremities. Second-degree burns were detected in 85.8% of the patients, and third-degree burns were detected in 14.2%. The median length of stay was 11 days, and a positive correlation was found between TBSA and age and length of stay ($p < 0.001$). Flame and electrical burns were associated with higher total body surface area in older children. There was no significant difference between gender and burn type. Flame burns required longer hospital stays and more frequent debridement; grafting was applied least frequently in scalding, and escharotomy was applied most frequently in electrical burns. Flame and electrical burns were associated with higher mortality ($p < 0.05$). Our study suggests that pediatric burns occurring in situations such as war and conflict may directly or indirectly affect children's clinics. Pediatric burns occurring during this period affect a larger surface area, cause deeper tissue damage, and therefore have higher surgical intervention and mortality rates compared to peacetime burns.

INTRODUCTION

Considering the war and terror incidents experienced worldwide, it is seen that one in ten children is directly or indirectly affected by these situations. This impact can occur in physical, psychological, and social dimensions, both directly and indirectly. In conflict environments, children are directly targeted by warring groups; sometimes, children are forced to join armed groups or provide support to these groups. This situation causes serious physical trauma to children.¹

Thermal injuries due to wars are one of the most common and devastating body damage, especially seen in the pediatric period. Pediatric burns occurring in war environments represent a difficult medical condition to treat for both military and civilian health workers, as they require intensive therapeutic and surgical interventions. Despite all intensive treatment efforts, such injuries are among the leading causes of mortality and morbidity in children.²

The Syrian civil war, which started in 2011, has caused many children to be negatively affected physically and psychologically. Civilian and pediatric injuries occurring in war environments are mostly treated in safer neighboring countries. Hatay province of Turkey is located on the Syrian-Turkish border. In this context, Turkey has become one of the main countries where children injured in the Syrian civil war are treated.³

This study aims to evaluate the clinical characteristics of pediatric cases brought to our country due to burns caused by the Syrian civil war and to contribute to the literature with the findings obtained.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted as a single-center, retrospective analysis covering burn cases under the age of 18 who were treated as inpatients at the Hatay Education and Research Hospital Burn Unit between 01.01.2011-31.12.2024.

Hatay province, where the study was conducted, is located in the southernmost part of Turkey and borders Syria on the southern and eastern borders. The distance between Hatay city center and the Syrian border is approximately 50 kilometers. Due to this geographical location, Hatay plays a critical role in transporting injured civilians affected by the Syrian civil war, especially pediatric patients, to healthcare services.

Patient data were obtained from the hospital automation system and physical files of the patients. During the study period, 1948 Syrian burn cases were brought to our hospital emergency department, 144 of the cases were treated as outpatients, 516 were referred due to lack of space in the clinic, 1288 cases were treated as inpatients, and 984 cases whose data were reached were included in the study. The patients' age, gender, cause of burn, degree and percentage of burn, burn areas, presence of additional interventions, length of stay, and mortality status were evaluated. The pediatric Lund and Browder Chart scale was used to calculate the burn percentage. Certain exclusion criteria were applied when determining the cases to be included in the study. Accordingly, individuals over the age of 18, pediatric cases hospitalized for reasons other than burns, patients brought from outside Syria or directly from our country due to burns, and cases whose medical records could not be accessed were excluded from the study.

In our study, data analysis was performed with SPSS version 22. Median, range, minimum, and maximum values were used in the presentation of quantitative data; number of cases (n) and percentiles (%) were used in the presentation of qualitative data. The distributions of quantitative data were evaluated with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Kruskal-Wallis test was used in the comparison of quantitative data with qualitative data; Spearman correlation analysis was used in the comparison of quantitative data with other quantitative data. The chi-square test was used in the comparison of qualitative data. $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS

In our study, the median age of the patients was 7 years (IQR: 8 years), and 79.2% were male. The most common cause of

burns was flame burns (72.4%), followed by scalding (25.4%) and electrical/contact burns (2.2%). The median total burn surface area (TBSA) was determined as 23% (IQR: 16%); the most common burn area was the anterior trunk with 86.2%, followed by the head and neck region (66.6%) and upper extremities (52.5%). At least second-degree burn depth was detected in 85.8% of the patients, and at least third-degree burn depth was detected in 14.2%. The median hospital stay was found as 11 days (IQR: 10 days). Surgical debridement was applied to 42.9% of the patients, grafting to 28.6%, and fasciotomy/escharotomy to 13.6%. The mortality rate was determined as 13.3% (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Burn Patients

Variable	Value
Age, Median (IQR)	7 years (IQR: 8)
Gender, n (%)	
Male	779 (79.2%)
Female	205 (20.8%)
Cause of Burn, n (%)	
Flame	712 (72.4%)
Scald	250 (25.4%)
Electrical/Contact	22 (2.2%)
Burn Surface Area, Median (IQR)	23% (IQR: 16)
Burn Location, n (%)	
Head	655 (66.6%)
Anterior Trunk	848 (86.2%)
Posterior Trunk	396 (40.2%)
Arm	517 (52.5%)
Legs	298 (30.3%)
Burn Depth, n (%)	
First + Second Degree	844 (85.8%)
First + Second + Third Degree	140 (14.2%)
Length of Hospital Stay, Median (IQR)	11 days (IQR: 10)
Additional Interventions, n (%)	
Debridement	422 (42.9%)
Grafting	281 (28.6%)
Fasciotomy/Escharotomy	133 (13.6%)
Mortality, n (%)	131 (13.3%)

In our study, the median burn percentage in head burns was determined as 10% (IQR: 5), 11% (IQR: 5) for the anterior trunk, 11% (IQR: 6) for the posterior trunk, 8% (IQR: 4) for the upper extremities and 8% (IQR: 4) for the lower extremities. The burn percentage of the head/neck and anterior

trunk was found to be significantly higher in flame burns ($p = 0.049$ and $p = 0.004$, respectively). In contrast, the burn percentage of the upper extremities was found to be statistically significantly higher in electrical burns ($p: 0.009$). No significant relationship was found between the burn type and the burn rates of the posterior trunk and lower extremities ($p=0.086$ and $p = 0.318$, respectively) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Relationship between burn shape and body localizations

A positive correlation was found between the burn percentage of the patients, age, and hospitalization duration ($r: 0.121$, $p<0.001$ and $r: 0.555$, $p<0.001$, respectively) (Table 2).

Table 2. Relationship Between Age, Burn Percentage, and Length of Hospital Stay

	Burn Percentage (%)	
	r	p
Age (years)	0.121	<0.001
Length of Stay (days)	0.555	<0.001

In our study, the mean age of pediatric patients with flame and electrical burns was significantly higher than those with scald burns ($p < 0.05$). Although the proportion of male patients was high in all burn types, no significant difference was found between gender and burn type ($p > 0.05$). Total burn surface area (TBSA) was found to be higher in flame burns than in other burn types, while the lowest TBSA was observed in electrical burns ($p < 0.05$). When the regional distribution was evaluated, scald and flame burns were most frequently seen in the head and trunk regions, while electrical burns were most frequently observed in the arms and feet ($p < 0.05$). Arranging the burn width range, second-degree burns were more common in scald cases, and third-degree burns were most frequently listed in electrical burns ($p < 0.05$). When evaluated according to burn etiologies, the flame burn degree at

admission was found to be significantly longer ($p < 0.05$). While debridement is most frequently applied in flame burn cases, the grafting rate is lowest in scald burns, and the escharotomy application rate is significantly higher in electrical burns ($p < 0.05$). In addition, individual mortality rates in flame and electrical/contact burns can be adjusted significantly higher by taking into account ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 3. Relationship Between Burn Type and Clinical Characteristics

Clinical Characteristic	Flame (n=712)	Scald (n=250)	Electrical/Contact (n=22)	p-value
Age, Median (IQR), years	10 (7)	3 (4)	7.5 (10)	<0.001
Gender				0.094
Male, n(%)	576 (80.9%)	187 (74.8%)	16 (72.7%)	
Female, n (%)	136 (19.1%)	63 (25.2%)	6 (27.3%)	
Burn Surface Area, Median (IQR), %	24 (16)	21 (14)	17 (9)	0.011
Burn Location				
Head, n (%)	496 (69.7%)	156 (62.4%)	3 (13.6%)	<0.001
Anterior Torso, n (%)	628 (88.2%)	216 (86.4%)	4 (18.2%)	<0.001
Posterior Torso, n (%)	305 (42.8%)	90 (36.0%)	1 (4.5%)	<0.001
Arm, n (%)	373 (52.4%)	124 (49.6%)	20 (90.9%)	0.001
Legs, n (%)	217 (30.5%)	67 (26.8%)	14 (63.6%)	0.001
Burn Severity				<0.001
Second-degree, n (%)	607 (85.3%)	227 (90.8%)	10 (45.5%)	
Third-degree, n (%)	105 (14.7%)	23 (9.2%)	12 (54.5%)	
Length of Hospital Stay, Median (IQR), days	12 (11)	11 (2)	10 (14)	0.002
Additional Interventions				
Debridement, n (%)	330 (46.3%)	86 (34.4%)	6 (27.3%)	0.001
Grafting, n (%)	202 (28.0%)	69 (27.6%)	10 (45.5%)	0.024
Escharotomy, n (%)	103 (14.5%)	18 (7.2%)	12 (54.5%)	<0.001
Mortality, n (%)	102 (14.2%)	17 (6.8%)	13 (59.1%)	<0.001

DISCUSSION

More than 1.5 million people were injured, and more than 320,000 people lost their lives due to the civil war that started in Syria in 2011. Approximately 12,000 of these casualties were children. Children injured in the war are transferred to neighboring countries and treated in these countries, depending on the severity of the trauma. Turkey has an important position among these countries due to its land border with Syria and accepts a high number of pediatric trauma cases.³

Pediatric patients with extensive TBSA burns, burns of specific regions (joints, genital area, etc.), inhalation injuries, electrical burns, and accompanying comorbidities should be hospitalized and treated. Such cases should be managed by multidisciplinary teams consisting of pediatricians, plastic surgeons, surgeons experienced in burns, intensive care specialists, and anesthesiologists.⁴

In many studies conducted on pediatric burn cases, it has been reported that children with burns are often between the ages of 1 and 5, and 55-58% of the cases are male.⁵⁻⁸ In the study conducted by Borgman et al. on the conflict periods in Iraq and Afghanistan, isolated burn cases were evaluated; it was reported that the median age of the cases was 4 years, and 67% of the patients were male.⁹ In our study, the median age of the patients was determined as 7 years. It was observed that the mean age of pediatric patients with flame and electrical burns was significantly higher than other burn types, and a positive correlation was also determined between age and total burn surface area (TBSA). In all patient groups, male gender (79.2%) was dominant, and no statistically significant relationship was found between gender and burn type ($p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that especially male children over a certain age are not only passive victims in war environments, but also become a direct or indirect part of the conflicts. Children's presence in active conflict zones puts them at high risk of exposure to serious traumatic agents such as high-voltage power lines, explosives, and contact with flames. This shows that children living in conflict environments without protection can result in physical trauma, and these traumas often lead to advanced burns.

Many studies have shown that the most common pediatric burn application is scalding with hot liquids (56.7-88.7%), followed by flame burns (7.2-17.6%) (6, 10-13). Borgman et al. reported that 84% of pediatric cases in war-torn regions were burned due to war-related causes.⁹ Sarsu et al. reported in

their study comparing pediatric burn cases in Syria and Türkiye that Syrian children were more frequently admitted to the hospital due to flame burns.¹⁴ In a study conducted in Africa, where civil conflicts were experienced, the distribution of burn causes by age groups was examined, and it was shown that scalding injuries decreased with age. While scalding accounts for 79% of burns in the 0-4 age group, this rate drops to 61% in the 5-9 age group and 51% in the 10-12 age group.¹⁵ In our study, flame burns (72.4%) were found to be the most common cause of burns, followed by scalding (25.4%) and electrical/contact burns (2.2%). The high rate of flame burns may be related to fires and explosions resulting from bomb attacks, improvised explosive devices (IEDs) being accessible to children, and uncontrolled use of flammable materials for heating or cooking.

In studies conducted on non-war pediatric burns, it has been stated that more than 70% of pediatric burns have TBSAs less than 10%, and the most frequently affected areas are the upper extremities, trunk, and head and neck.^{5, 6, 8, 10, 12} It has been stated that TBSA is at least 20% in individuals who survived burns that occurred in conventional wars or terrorist attacks.¹⁶ In a study conducted, war-related burns were evaluated, and the median burn percentage of surviving cases was reported as 15% and the average as 25%.⁹ Sarsu et al. reported that TBSA was higher in children in Syria (13%; 24%) in a study comparing pediatric burn cases in Syria and Turkey.¹⁴ In South Africa, the most frequently affected areas in pediatric burn injuries were reported as head and neck (27%), trunk (27%), and upper extremities (28%), respectively.¹⁵ In our study, the median TBSA of the patients was 23%; the most common burn area was the frontal body with 86.2%, followed by the head and neck region (66.6%) and upper extremities (52.5%). Flame scalding and flame burns were most frequently seen in the head and trunk regions, while electrical burns were most frequently observed in the arms and legs. No significant relationship was found between the burn type and the burn rates on the back of the trunk and lower extremities. These findings, consistent with the literature, show that thermal burns caused by war and terror events affect larger surface areas and lead to more devastating results. Direct exposure of the frontal body to heat, especially due to explosions or glowing fuels, explains the high rate of head/neck and frontal body burns. In addition, clothing ignition increases the burn rates on both the trunk and upper extremities; children's curious grasping of bare electrical

cables stands out as another factor that increases the frequency and percentage of upper extremity burns.

Wesson et al. reported that 66% of children burned in Africa had moderate burn severity.¹⁵ Uçak et al. evaluated adult and pediatric burn cases together in their study and stated that 33% of the cases had 3rd-degree burn findings (source).¹⁷ In our study, at least second-degree burns were detected in 85.8% of the patients, and third-degree burns were detected in 14.2%; second-degree burns were more common in scalding cases, and third-degree burns were most frequently seen in electrical burns. This situation leads to the idea that high-energy traumas (bomb attacks, IEDs, high voltage power lines, etc.) occurring in war environments may cause deeper and more extensive burns in children. In addition, inadequate treatment in war zones and delays in referral due to many reasons, especially security, may have led to an increase in deep burn rates.

Jordan et al. (6) found the length of stay in pediatric burn patients to be 10 days, Ruan et al.¹⁸ found the mean length of stay in pediatric burns to be 12.6 days; they emphasized that etiology and TBSA are highly correlated with length of stay. Mobayed et al. stated in their study that the length of stay in hospital in pediatric burns is directly correlated with TBSA.¹⁸ Sarsu et al. found in their study comparing pediatric burn cases in Syria and Türkiye that the length of stay in hospital in Syrian burn cases was 18 days, while the length of stay in Turkish children was 9.5 days, and this difference was significant.¹⁴ In our study, the median length of stay in hospital in pediatric patients was found to be 11 days (IQR: 10 days), and a positive significant relationship was found between length of stay and total burn surface area (TBSA). It was found that the length of stay in flame burns was significantly longer compared to other types of burns. These findings suggest that flame burns are more complex to treat and take longer to heal due to deeper and more widespread tissue damage. In addition, since the risk of infection, fluid loss, surgical intervention, and grafting is higher in flame burns, the length of hospital stay is significantly longer.

Jordan et al. reported that almost half of pediatric burn patients required additional intervention.⁶ Liu et al. reported that intervention was needed in 25.3% of pediatric burns.⁵ Han et al. reported that although the TBSA of electrical burns was the lowest, the frequency of surgical intervention was high in electrical and contact burns.¹¹ Sarsu et al. reported that the frequency of fasciotomy/escharotomy and grafts was higher in pediatric burn cases coming from war zones.¹⁴ Our study

determined that 42.9% of patients underwent surgical debridement, 28.6% underwent grafting, and 13.6% underwent fasciotomy/escharotomy, and these interventions were particularly concentrated in electrical burns. These findings indicate that pediatric burns occurring under war conditions lead to both deeper and more complex clinical presentations. The high surgical intervention requirement of electrical burns despite low TBSA can be explained by the fact that such injuries frequently damage deep tissue, nerves, and vascular structures.

It has been stated that the mortality rate in pediatric burn cases during the war in Iraq and Afghanistan was 13.2% (9). Sarsu et al. reported that the mortality rate was 4.3% in their study and that children with burns brought from the war zone were more mortal.¹⁴ In our study, the mortality rate was 13.3%, and the highest mortality rate was in electrical burns. Our mortality rate is consistent with the literature, and the mortality rate may be higher because flame and electrical burns generally cause deeper tissue damage and systemic complications.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our study shows that pediatric burns occurring in situations such as war and conflict can directly or indirectly affect children's clinics. Pediatric burns occurring during this period affect a larger surface area compared to burns during peacetime, cause deeper tissue damage, and therefore have higher surgical intervention and mortality rates.

The limitations of the study are related to the retrospective nature of the study and the difficulties encountered in the data collection processes. For this reason, it has not been clearly determined to what extent and for what reasons patients were referred to external centers. In addition, treatment algorithms could not be accessed due to the damage to the physical archives of the hospital in the earthquake in Hatay province.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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No

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